

From the Desk of Sf. R. Careaga

Responding to “the Cosmic Hoax”

July 15, 2021

To Whom It May Interest;

I was asked for a response to the following video <https://youtu.be/zP95OISG0NI> “The Cosmic Hoax” by S. Greer. I want to note that to understand this video, in its totality, is that it can be summed up as having the following hypotheses:

- That aliens are real and have been studied by the government for over 100 years
- UFOs began as their visits to us and became secret US government programs
- ET’s mean us well and are concerned for our behavior and future; ie they desire companionship
- ET’s are part of our same dimension only
- ET’s are not desiring conflict with us
- The CIA and/or other government agencies have promulgated a false hoax narrative of ET threat in order to gin up need for the Military Industrial Complex to create more and more space weaponry
- The MIC is addicted to fear, power, and greed (control) of the world population so they pretend to be agnostic or ignorant of alien coverup “facts” and send disinformation specialists to engage in a form of psychological warfare (psyops) with the public and alien researchers/enthusiasts worldwide
 - Some of these people are well known names.

My response is (frankly speaking) as follows...

The videography style is specific to targeting of altstream persons, particularly conspiracy theorists. It is, like Zeitgeist, however designed to appeal to “rationalism” in the form of appeals and apologies. It shows glimpses of secret documents and clandestine meetings, but is not too giving or generous in terms of the names and locations of these documents. In general it relies upon the (apparently) obvious expertise of the interviewees, particularly Dr. Greer and a son of the Melon family. Its main touch to the EPEMC subject comes through the discussion of Electro-gravitic/kinetic drives, particularly in military craft. But it offers no definitive proof. However, it does have a reasonable timeline. The ‘documentary’ also makes it explicitly clear that it is anti-government especially with the Roswell Coverup, which is 100% a real crash (among others).

My response to this is that it is a neat new line for the alien/coverup/UFO community to now follow. Imagine a situation where the progenitors of Y2K needed to fall back on an end of the world scenario... but then after May of 2012 are running out of leg room to run. They will need to alter the schedule or provide provisions to explain the mistakes. While it is true that there is far more tangible (video) evidence than before, the sources are often the same named “suspected” sources the documentary will decry: particularly the corporate media and the US Military. All of these new lines of evidence and thinking *themselves* seem like a convenient psyop (or at least a book selling scheme), and tend to provide little new evidence. If the US Government cannot be trusted (this is true), and if the media is owned by families of fascist oligarchs, then why rely upon their “open and honest” admissions now? This is illogical.

My greater reaction to the new strain of UFOlogy is that, again, if we focus upon building a more just, modern, PEM-based, egalitarian, anti-Communist society, based on humanistic principles and reliant upon the PEM and rationalism... returning us essentially to the Great Enlightenment. Without this focus, it seems certain that we will continue to see fake cosmologies and pseudosciences dominate the landscape, each enabling one another in a contest of skeptical wit. Skepticism is healthy, but when we get to the point of Flat Earth resurgence, we can know for certain that skeptical people are not getting access to the right kind of scientific knowledge. Is this a CIA or Big Oil or MIC plot? Probably. But the wider issue is that the people themselves, be they skeptics or common movie goers, or “journalists”, what have you, are actively involved in anti-rationalist discourse. It is fine to propose any hypothesis you want. But then you need to provide a means to test it. If it is a pseudoscientific hypothesis, the most common thing to do is nothing. That’s typically what we see. Or if there is “something” it is usually conference circuits and selling books, “waking people up” (to what is never 100% clear to the dog being wagged by the tail). There is literally a “WAKE UP” yell done in this video which is completely out of context. The source video is an “SJW” woman with mental illness, having a meltdown about politics. It has nothing at all to do with aliens or UFOs. From here we can see the sort of pseudo-ethical standards and manipulation tone the documentary is deigned to have. If you are likely to believe them, then you will not notice these manipulations. If you are predisposed to skepticism, you might believe portions and overall hate the film. If you are a total skeptic, you will trash the video and the makers will say “it’s not for you, you haven’t opened your eyes yet.”

From an EPEMC perspective, the question is what quality level (research, scientific, sociological perhaps) value does it provide? At best level C data or evidence, mostly level D. There is a lot of third or fourth hand knowledge passed on as fact. There is also a literal “we must believe Dr. Greer” line in the film which is eyebrow raising. Again from an EPEMC perspective, even for the discussion of overlay of the ancient architects with the PEMC, it’s not of significant or useful value.

The other tired or cliché new quality of this new strain of thought is the inclusion of what was termed “exo-racism.” While I agree mankind has an inordinate amount of xenophobia to extraterrestrials, the mechanism for it is not obviously racist. First that term is far overused, especially today. And it seems like pandering for a new or younger audience (to buy books). Secondly, green, gray, literal black, and hyperdimensional are not race colors. Were men of the mid 20th century government overwhelmingly caucasian? Yes. But traditionally higher IQ people have had decreased amounts of racism as a definitive rule for behavior. Many black scientists succeeded at NASA for this reason. At any rate it is apples and oranges. It was a sort of “Cringe” moment in the documentary that appeared to want to “go woke” to pander to a certain left-leaning audience. But traditionally “conspiracy theorist” circles are in a Libertarian or right-leaning (certainly Independent) bent, and it doesn’t seem likely this will aid the stream of thought to make a deep penetration. It might be that Dr. Greer himself has a political axe to grind? Either way it seemed rather out of place. It’s certainly something we wouldn’t want to see emulated in other altstream research circles. “Wokism” is inherently anti-rational and anti-science.

Hopefully this clarifies the issue for the readers who want to discuss aliens and UFOs more in EPEMC context. However, the best work done (outside of my own) so far, has been the skeptical response from the Thunderbolts Project detailing the behaviors of plasmoids as compared to the UFO phenomenon. Beyond that, we don’t really have enough data to draw any final conclusions. Plenty of anecdote, but rarely does any of it form a cohesive narrative.

Sincerely,
Shifu Careaga